

RISK & MANAGEMENT & QUALITY ASSURANCE PLAN

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1. Executive Summary

This document is the deliverable “D7.2 – Risk and Management and Quality Assurance plan” of the Horizon Europe project “eCREAM enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine through automated data extraction” (hereinafter also referred to as “eCREAM”, project number: 101057726).

This document aims to outline the quality assurance and risk management plans and the relevant procedures to be adopted by the consortium to maintain a high level of quality in the eCREAM implementation and its outcomes. It contains rules, mechanisms and processes established in order to proceed during the 5 years of this project in the best way, taking care also of potential risks that could be faced.

In conjunction with the Consortium Agreement, the “Risk & management & quality assurance plan” also serves as a core reference for the consortium organisation, and it will be updated if required.

2. Project Overview

The eCREAM - enabling Clinical Research in Emergency and Acute care Medicine - project is a 5-year Horizon Europe project led by the Mario Negri Institute for Pharmacological Research (IRFMN, Italy).

The eCREAM consortium includes 11 partners from 8 European countries (France, Greece, Italy, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia, Switzerland, UK).

The project’s central aim is to enable clinical and quality of care assessment research using data extracted directly from Electronic Health Records (EHR) of Emergency Departments (ED).

To reach this goal, eCREAM has three main objectives:

- to develop new technical solutions to extract reliable clinical information from structured and unstructured data contained in different electronic patient files;
- to pilot the exploitation of the established databases in two relevant use cases: i) assessment of ED propensity to hospitalise a patient, and ii) development of a dashboard to be used by citizens and policymakers to improve the quality of care in ED;
- to FAIRify (i.e., making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable) the established databases for clinicians, researchers, health policymakers, and citizens while respecting the European and national legislations.

3. Work packages and tasks responsibilities

3.1 Work packages and tasks

As set in the Grant Agreement, the coordination of each Work Package (WP) is appointed to one partner, referred to as the “WP leader”. All WPs are also divided into tasks, which are managed by a “task leader”. Responsibilities for each WP and each task are shown below.

WP AND TASKS		LEADER
WP1	Natural Language Processing for EHR	FBK
T1.1	Context analysis and task definition	IRFMN
T1.2	Data collection	IRFMN
T1.3	NLP Development	FBK
T1.4	Evaluation and Analysis	FBK
T1.5	Results' Deployment	FBK
WP AND TASKS		LEADER
WP2	Data extraction module	ASTIR
T2.1	Analysis of the operative context	IRFMN
T2.2	Analysis of the technological context	ASTIR
T2.3	Interface specifications for the existing systems	ASTIR
T2.4	Interface specifications for the new ED-EHR	ASTIR
T2.5	Development of interface modules on the eCREAM side	ASTIR
T2.6	Development of interface modules on the side of hospital systems and technical support	ASTIR
WP AND TASKS		LEADER
WP3	Design and Development of the ED-EHR	FBK
T3.1	Context analysis	FBK
T3.2	Domain analysis	IRFMN
T3.3	Conceptual design of the ED-EHR architecture	FBK
T3.4	Design and development of the Database model, the business logic components, and the user interface	FBK
T3.5	Design and development of the reasoner module	FBK
T3.6	Design/development of the APIs and modules for interoperability	FBK
T3.7	Test Deployment and Support	ASTIR
WP AND TASKS		LEADER
WP4	Use cases	IRFMN
T4.1	Drafting the protocol	IRFMN
T4.2	Ethics committee approval	IRFMN
T4.3	Data collection and extraction	IRFMN
T4.4	Data analysis and results reporting	IRFMN
T4.5	Training of EDs in using the quality-of-care indicators to enable self-assessment	IRFMN
T4.6	Drafting the protocol	IRFMN
T4.7	Ethics committee approval	IRFMN
T4.8	Data extraction	IRFMN
T4.9	Data analysis and results reporting	IRFMN
T4.10	Development and release of the dashboards to inform end-users about real-time characteristics of the EDs	ASTIR

WP AND TASKS		LEADER
WP5	FAIRification and ELSI compliance	ECRIN
T5.1	Ensuring compliance with ethical and legal requirements	ECRIN
T5.2	Establishing the FAIRification strategy and workflows of databases and services	ECRIN
T5.3	Integration of the databases and services to the MIP	CHUV
T5.4	Embedding the eCREAM outputs to relevant European initiatives	ECRIN
WP AND TASKS		LEADER
WP6	eCREAM integrated platform	ASTIR
T6.1	Analysis of the functional requirements	ASTIR
T6.2	Design and develop the eCREAM Translation Manager	ASTIR
T6.3	Design of the platform architecture	ASTIR
T6.4	Installation of the platform infrastructure and modules	ASTIR
T6.5	Platform test, corrective and adaptive maintenance	ASTIR
WP AND TASKS		LEADER
WP7	Project coordination	IRFMN
T7.1	Scientific coordination and project management	IRFMN
T7.2	Administrative and financial management	IRFMN
T7.3	Risk management and quality assurance	IRFMN
WP AND TASKS		LEADER
WP8	Dissemination, exploitation and communication	IRFMN
T8.1	Development of eCREAM dissemination, communication and exploitation plan	IRFMN
T8.2	Scientific dissemination	IRFMN
T8.3	Website, social media and other communications materials	IRFMN
T8.4	Networking	IRFMN
T8.5	Exploitation strategy	IRFMN
T8.6	Activities related to “Innovative tools for EHRs and patient registries’ cluster”	IRFMN

3.2 Responsibilities of the Coordinator

The Coordinator has the following responsibilities:

- Monitoring the overall implementation of all WPs and project activities;
- Ensuring the smooth implementation of the work programme;
- Ensuring that the project’s objectives are met to the highest standards;
- Ensuring that all necessary resources are available for the implementation of the project;
- Ensuring that all deliverables are submitted in due time on the Participant Portal;
- Ensuring the dissemination of public deliverables, once they are approved by the European Commission (EC).

3.3 Responsibilities of WP leaders

WP leaders have the following responsibilities:

- Coordinating the implementation of their WP;
- Monitoring the implementation and the coordination of the different tasks of their WP;
- Ensuring that all deliverables are delivered and submitted in due time.

3.4 Responsibilities of task Leaders

Tasks leaders have the following responsibilities:

- Monitoring the implementation of their respective tasks;
- Coordinating the production and submission of the deliverables they are responsible for, in coordination with contributors.

In addition, the Coordinator and WP leaders must be in regular communication to ensure the straightforward implementation of the work plan and that necessary steps are taken to settle any issues or challenges that may emerge. WP leaders must also work closely with task leaders to ensure that their WP meets the project's objectives.

4. Quality assurance

4.1 General principles

The aim of a Quality Assurance Plan is to ensure compliance with the relevant quality standards. This Plan wants to define suitable quality management processes, including mechanisms to review internal reports and project deliverables.

First of all, it is essential that project activities and results comply with the project's objectives. Indeed, this Plan will permit the close monitoring of the implementation of the project's activities and the delivery of the best results.

Besides, it is important to keep in mind the end users of the tools eCREAM will develop. Indeed, this Plan will ensure those tools will meet the needs of principal stakeholders and citizens within the project and beyond.

4.2 Monitoring of the implementation of the project

The Coordinator will closely monitor the implementation of all project activities and ensure that all necessary technical and financial resources are available. As described in the Consortium Agreement, there will be regular coordination meetings with project partners to review the implementation of the project and address any issues that may arise. In addition, the Coordinator will carefully monitor the implementation of the project through the interim and periodic financial reports produced by the project's partners.

4.3 Production of deliverables

4.3.1 Responsibilities

Partners have the following responsibilities:

- Task leaders will ensure that deliverables are produced on time, with high-quality standards, and meet the objectives set out in the Grant Agreement. To this end, they will be responsible for elaborating a plan and coordinating the drafting of the deliverable in cooperation with pre-identified

contributors and peer reviewers. After the final review, the task leader will be responsible for uploading the deliverable on the dedicated portal;

- The Coordinator will be responsible for the final review of the deliverable; he will also ensure that the task leader will finalize its submission on the portal. If partners would face any challenges or difficulties in the process, the Coordinator is also responsible for assisting task leaders and partners in finding solutions for the smooth production of the deliverable.

4.3.2 Deliverable production plan

Task leaders must ensure the timely production of high-quality deliverables.

To this end, they will establish an outline detailing their plan for the production of each deliverable, three weeks before the submission deadline, that they will share with pre-identified contributors and peer reviewers.

This plan will include the following information:

- A timeline for the production of the deliverable;
- Involved partners;
- Peer reviewers;
- Proposed outline of the deliverable.

4.3.3 Drafting process

The task leader will produce a first draft of the deliverable that will be shared with all contributors to their task, as defined in the GA. After receiving their input, task leaders will draft an updated version of the deliverable that will be sent to pre-identified peer reviewers.

4.3.4 Peer-review

To ensure that the project's objectives are met and its results fit endusers' needs, deliverables will be reviewed by selected partners and, more particularly, by the partner cities, tentatively two weeks before the submission deadline. In addition, the project's Expert Advisory Board will conduct reviews of some deliverables, thus providing external expertise and knowledge.

To facilitate the process, task leaders will develop a series of questions for peer reviewers.

4.3.5 Final review

The deliverable will be sent to the Coordinator (IRFMN), tentatively one week before the submission deadline, who will do a final review. IRFMN will check the conformity of the deliverable to the project's objectives, the quality of the content as well as the correct application of established templates and logos. IRFMN will then send the approved deliverable back to the task leader in order to make its submission to the European Commission via the participant portal.

The Coordinator will also ensure that relevant public deliverables are published on the project's website and disseminated to a wider audience.

The process and responsibilities for the production of each deliverable are summarised below:

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D1.1	Requirements and task definition	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP1	PU - Public	12

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D1.2	Collection of EHRs and their annotation, Cycle I	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP1	SEN - Sensitive	24

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D1.3	Collection of EHRs and their annotation, Cycle II	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP1	SEN - Sensitive	42

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D1.4	Performance of NLP models, Cycle I	FBK

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP1	PU - Public	33

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D1.5	Performance of NLP models, Cycle II	FBK

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP1	PU - Public	54

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D2.1	Analysis of operative and technological context	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP2	PU - Public	12

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D2.2	Testing of eCREAM interface modules	ASTIR

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP2	PU - Public	24

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D2.3	Testing of hospital systems' interface modules	ASTIR

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP2	PU - Public	36

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D3.1	First release of the ED-EHR contents	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP3	SEN - Sensitive	12

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D3.2	Architectural design	FBK

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP3	PU - Public	27

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D3.3	First release of the reasoner module	FBK

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP3	SEN - Sensitive	36

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D3.4	System test and Deployment documentation	FBK

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP3	PU - Public	50

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
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D3.5	User manuals	FBK
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Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
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WP3	PU - Public	54
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Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
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D4.1	Study initiation package for clinical study 1	IRFMN
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Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
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WP4	PU - Public	6
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Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
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D4.2	Study initiation package for clinical study 2	IRFMN
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Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
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WP4	PU - Public	6
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Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
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D4.3	Midterm recruited report for clinical study 1	IRFMN
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Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
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WP4	PU - Public	46
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Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
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D4.4	Midterm recruited report for clinical study 2	IRFMN
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Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
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WP4	PU - Public	46
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Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
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D4.5	Nowcasting model	Orobix
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Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
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WP4	SEN - Sensitive	50
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Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D4.6	Multivariable model	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP4	PU - Public	50

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D4.7	First release of the dashboards for use case 2	ASTIR

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP4	SEN - Sensitive	54

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D4.8	Results of clinical study 1 in public repository	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP4	PU - Public	58

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D4.9	Results of clinical study 2 in public repository	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP4	PU - Public	58

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D4.10	General and personalised reports of use case 1	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP4	PU - Public	60

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D5.1	Draft data-sharing management plan	ECRIN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP5	PU - Public	6

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D5.2	Integration of db and services to the MIP	CHUV

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP5	PU - Public	48

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D5.3	Updated data-sharing management plan	ECRIN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP5	PU - Public	55

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D6.1	First release of the Translation Manager	ASTIR

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP6	SEN - Sensitive	12

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D6.2	Platform functional requirements	ASTIR

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP6	PU - Public	24

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D6.3	Outlining the platform architecture design	ASTIR

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP6	SEN - Sensitive	36

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D7.1	Consortium Agreement	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP7	PU - Public	3

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D7.2	Risk and Management and Quality Assurance Plan	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP7	PU - Public	3

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D7.3	Feedback from Participants' ethics advisory boards	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP7	PU - Public	12

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D8.1	eCREAM website	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP8	PU - Public	3

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D8.2	Research cluster website with eCREAM contribution	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP8	PU - Public	12

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D8.3	Communication, dissemination, exploitation 1	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP8	PU - Public	18

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D8.4	First scientific paper	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP8	PU - Public	24

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D8.5	Communication, dissemination, exploitation 2	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP8	PU - Public	36

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Name	Lead Beneficiary
D8.6	Final communication, dissemination, exploitation	IRFMN

Work Package No	Dissemination Level	Due Date (month)
WP8	PU - Public	60

5. Management of risks

5.1 Risk Management Plan

The Coordinator, with the support of project partners, is responsible for establishing a Risk Management plan. The aim of this Plan is to identify, at an early stage, any possible risks that may arise in the implementation of the project and find solutions in due time. This Plan specifies risk management procedures and responsibilities.

The Risk Management Plan is defined according to the following elements:

- risk identification, which aims to identify risks of any nature that may arise in the context of the project;
- risk analysis, which evaluates the likelihood of each risk and its potential impact on the project;
- contingency actions, which aims to identify the measures and the processes which should be undertaken to manage risks.

The coordinator and WP leaders will review the accuracy of identified risks every six months, and the plan will be improved and completed accordingly.

5.2 Risk Monitoring and Mitigation

There are four primary elements involved with risk monitoring activities:

- systematically track the status of risks previously identified;
- identify, document, and assess any new risks that emerge;
- effectively manage the risk reserve;
- capture lessons learned for future risk identification and assessment efforts.

The project coordinator, WP leaders and task leaders must constantly monitor the evolution of the risks that may arise during the project. To this end, the coordinator and project partners have identified risks related to the implementation of their WPs and tasks, as well as proposed specific actions/measures to mitigate them.

These are presented in the table below, which includes:

- a description of each identified risk, an indication of the WPs in which this risk may arise;
- a measure of the risk assessment (likelihood and impact);
- a description of the proposed mitigation response.

RISK N°	WORK PACKAGE	DESCRIPTION
1	WP6, WP1, WP3, WP2, WP4	Different interdependent WPs or tasks operate at different speeds or do not align

LIKELIHOOD	IMPACT	PROPOSED MITIGATION MEASURES
Medium	Medium	Boost alignment efforts among work packages and tasks. Regular teleconferences to discuss progress and make necessary adjustments

RISK N°	WORK PACKAGE	DESCRIPTION
2	WP1	Collection of EHR reports proceeds at different speeds in different countries/hospitals due to various constraints (legislation, availability of IT specialists, etc.)

LIKELIHOOD	IMPACT	PROPOSED MITIGATION MEASURES
High	Medium	NLP development could be organized in series so as to start the task in time with the more efficient countries and leave more time for the latecomers

RISK N°	WORK PACKAGE	DESCRIPTION
3	WP2	Delay in the development of interface modules on the side of some hospital systems

LIKELIHOOD	IMPACT	PROPOSED MITIGATION MEASURES
High	Medium	Prioritise the development of the modules in the hospitals in line with expected times. The accumulated experience will speed up the process in the other hospitals

RISK N°	WORK PACKAGE	DESCRIPTION
4	WP3	Some modules of the new ED-EHR prove to be more complex to develop than expected

LIKELIHOOD	IMPACT	PROPOSED MITIGATION MEASURES
Medium	Low	The development plan could be reviewed to give priority to modules essential to allow the use in practice

RISK N°	WORK PACKAGE	DESCRIPTION
5	WP4	Impossibility for some centres to synchronise their systems with the eCREAM data extraction tool

LIKELIHOOD	IMPACT	PROPOSED MITIGATION MEASURES
Medium	Low	More data will be extracted from compliant centres to reach the expected sample size for running the predictive models

RISK N°	WORK PACKAGE	DESCRIPTION
6	WP5	Participants reluctant to share their data until the acceptance of key publications or other important milestones

LIKELIHOOD	IMPACT	PROPOSED MITIGATION MEASURES
Low	Low	Networking activity with external consortia will focus on the meaningful benefits of sharing data to convince reluctant participants. Develop a partner-specific approach to data sharing. The use of the MIP addresses concerns about handling sensitive data by partners external to the Consortium

RISK N°	WORK PACKAGE	DESCRIPTION
7	WP8	Key participant or PI leaves the project

LIKELIHOOD	IMPACT	PROPOSED MITIGATION MEASURES
Low	Medium	Participant will be replaced as soon as possible in agreement w/EC

RISK N°	WORK PACKAGE	DESCRIPTION
8	WP8	Delay in submission of key deliverables and milestones due to disagreement on scope and purpose

LIKELIHOOD	IMPACT	PROPOSED MITIGATION MEASURES
Low	Medium	Strategies for addressing this risk will be addressed in the Risk Management Plan. Conflict Resolution procedures should come into play if necessary

RISK N°	WORK PACKAGE	DESCRIPTION
9	WP8	Participants fail to agree due to different positions

LIKELIHOOD	IMPACT	PROPOSED MITIGATION MEASURES
Medium	Medium	Different communications methods can be implemented, leading to a common understanding

In the first months of this project, it seemed clear that our list of risks did not take care of all possible threats that eCREAM could face. For this reason, it became necessary to update it.

RISK N°	WORK PACKAGE	DESCRIPTION
10	WP1	Impossibility to have access to EHR clinical notes for one (or more) language(s)

LIKELIHOOD	IMPACT	PROPOSED MITIGATION MEASURES
Medium	High	Different learning methods for the NLP system can be implemented

RISK N°	WORK PACKAGE	DESCRIPTION
11	WP1, WP4, WP5	National legislations are stricter than GDPR, making it more difficult to collect sensitive data

LIKELIHOOD	IMPACT	PROPOSED MITIGATION MEASURES
High	High	Availing of ECRIN expertise and national legal experts, it will be developed a clear strategy to obtain the possibility to collect data in the shortest time possible

6. Conclusion

This deliverable aims to ensure the quality of the project’s results and outputs, as well as to identify and anticipate potential risks before they arise and ensure that proper action and mitigation steps are taken.

It will be updated if the project complexity will make it necessary.